

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE KEY FACTORS OF NUTRIENT FLUXES IN THREE TECHNIQUES OF AQUAPONIC SYSTEMS

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(Submitted: 29 Feb 2024; Accepted: 30 May 2024; Published: 25 June 2024)

ABSTRACT

Aquaponics, as a single ecosystem, requires optimal conditions for the life cycle of fish, beneficial bacteria, and plants that coexist in symbiosis. For effective interdependence, aquaponic systems need regular monitoring, effective control, and rapid correction of deviations in the environmental factors and hydrochemical indicators. The aim of this study was to quantitatively analyze the nutrient fluxes and the factors (air and water temperature, pH and DO level) on which they depend in three techniques aquaponic systems for tilapia and lettuce placed under identical conditions. The results showed that the quality of the air and water was within the optimal range, which ensured the steady state of the systems, symbiosis between the species in good conditions and, consequently. Our results suggest that combined diagnostics is a reliable method for optimizing symbiosis in aquaponics.

Key words: aquaponics health, aquaculture, plants, beneficial bacteria, water monitoring.

Introduction

The three different types of organisms in an aquaponic system (fish, plants and beneficial bacteria) exist together through symbiosis. The overall goal is to maintain suitable quality of the environment (air and water) for an optimal life cycle of all organisms in it (Endut et al. 2010; Mansor et al. 2023). The health of the species in this complex system and its integrity depend on the continuous monitoring of quality factors (Bittsanszky et al. 2016; Alselek et al. 2022).

The main process control indicators in the aquaponic cycle are the quality factors for hydroponics (air temperature and humidity, and water temperature) and for aquaculture (dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, ammonia content, nitrites and nitrates) (Alselek et al. 2022). Uncontrolled temperature and pH, together with low nitrogen and other nutrients, are the main reasons for low growth and yield of plant production (Tawaha et al. 2021). To solve this problem, an integrated autonomous control system is required for continuous monitoring and control of the dynamic processes (Shafeena 2016). The unstable characteristics (ammonium-nitrogen, nitrate-nitrogen, nitrite-nitrogen, pH, DO) change several times a day and are often interdependent; hence, the need for their testing on a daily basis (Masabni et al. 2020).

The aim of this study was to quantitatively analyze the nutrient fluxes and the factors (air and water temperature, pH and DO level) on which they depend in three techniques aquaponic systems (deep water culture (RAFT), nutrient film technique (NFT) and media grow bed (MGB)) for tilapia and lettuce placed under identical conditions.

Materials and methods

Aquaponic systems

The environmental parameters and water quality were studied in three aquaponic systems placed under equal conditions, rearing tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) (fingerlings (20 – 80 g) to mature fish (700 – 800 g)) and lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) (sprouting, growing, productivity) over a period of seven months (January to July 2023) to cover one fish life cycle and five lettuce harvests. The three main techniques of plant cultivation in aquaponic systems were observed at the Aquaponics Center, Bulgaria: deep water culture system (RAFT), nutrient film technique (NFT), and media grow bed (MGB). The following commercially available aquaponic systems were used: Clear Flow Aquaponic Systems®/version 2020 (F5) (Fig. 1 A), Large Commercial w/LFB Clear Flow Aquaponic Systems® with ZDEP®/version 2021 (LC) (Fig. 1 B) and Fish Nursery Clear Flow Aquaponic Systems®/version 2021 (FN) (Fig. 1 C) of Nelson and Pade®, Inc., Montello, Wisconsin, USA.

Figure 1: Aquaponic systems used in the study. (A): Clear Flow Aquaponic Systems®/version 2020 (F5); (B): Large Commercial w/LFB Clear Flow Aquaponic Systems® with ZDEP®/version 2021 (LC) and (C): Fish Nursery Clear Flow Aquaponic Systems®/version 2021 (FN) of Nelson and Pade®, Inc.

Control

The environmental parameters (temperature and air humidity in the greenhouse) were examined and reported daily using an innovative aquaponics health-monitoring system that incorporated high-tech back-end innovation sensors after putting the systems into operation. Data visualization and direct connection to a computer and smartphone interface system were used for monitoring (Pramono et al. 2023). Water temperature, pH, and DO were measured daily using a digital probe meter with an automatic control.

The parameters in aqueous solutions were investigated periodically by manual control: ammonium nitrogen ($\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$) and concentration of non-ionized ammonia (NH_3); ion-selective nitrite ($\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$) levels and nitrite concentration (NO_2); ion-selective nitrate ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) levels and nitrate concentration (NO_3). Octa-Slide 2 Comparator Tests of LaMotte Aquaponics Kit Code 3637 were used as comparison tests. The salicylate assay, diazotization/coupling reaction, and zinc reduction assay were used for the test factors ammonia, nitrite, and nitrate, respectively. The range and sensitivity of these methods were: salicylate assay from 0.0 to 2.0 mg/L $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$; diazotization/coupling reaction from 0.05 to 0.8 mg/L $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ and zinc reduction from 0.25 to 10.0 mg/L $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$. The method of Trussel (1972) was used to test the toxic non-ionized ammonia (NH_3).

The obtained ammonia-nitrogen values were multiplied by 1.2 to obtain the non-ionized ammonia values (1). The obtained nitrite-nitrogen values were multiplied by 3.3 to obtain the nitrite values (2), and those of nitrate-nitrogen, by 4.4 to obtain the nitrate values (3):

$$\text{Non-ionized ammonia (NH}_3\text{) mg/L} = \text{ammonia-nitrogen (NH}_3\text{-N)} \times 1.2 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Nitrite (NO}_2^- \text{) ppm} = \text{Nitrite-N (NO}_2\text{-N)} \times 3.3 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Nitrate (NO}_3^-) \text{ ppm} = \text{Nitrate-N (NO}_3\text{-N)} \times 4.4 \quad (3)$$

Statistical analysis

The data were processed by means of descriptive statistics and presented as mean \pm SD. The distribution was checked for normality by Kolmogorov-Smirnov & Lilliefors test. Because of small sample sizes a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's post hoc analysis was used to demonstrate significant differences in parameter values at $p < 0.05$ for the three systems. Statistical computations were performed using STATISTICA 8 for Windows (StatSoft Inc., USA).

Results and discussion

The air temperature during the monitoring period remained within the permissible range (14.4°C to 25.5°C, Nelson 2008) (Fig. 2, A). The average air temperature (°C) was significantly lower (17.14 ± 2.95 ; 17.51 ± 3.09 ; 17.54 ± 2.88) than the optimal values (21.13 ± 0.32 according to Nelson 2008) for the three systems in January ($p = 0.0198$) (Fig. 2, A). Reportedly, the optimal air temperature is in the range of 14.4°C to 25.5°C (Nelson 2008) and up to 30°C for lettuce (Yamori et al. 2022), which supports maximum plant growth. In June, on the other hand, the average air temperature for system F5 (32.57 ± 5.26) was significantly higher ($p = 0.0039$) as compared to the optimal (22.71 ± 0.56) (Fig. 2, A) and that for system LC (26.65 ± 2.62) ($p = 0.01762$) (Fig. 2 A).

Figure 2: Dynamics of air (A) and water (B) temperatures for the three systems (F5, LC and FN) for a period of seven months in 2023. Asterisks indicate significant differences from the optimal values (* - $p < 0.05$, ** - $p < 0.01$), and # indicates those between the F5 and LC systems. Red dashed lines indicate the upper and lower permissible limits for the air and water temperatures.

There were no significant differences in water temperature for the three systems compared to the optimal values for tilapia life: 25.5° – 26.6° C (Nelson 2008), during the observation period (Fig. 2, B).

The mean value (%) of relative air humidity in the last month of monitoring was significantly higher ($p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$) in the LC (41.85 ± 6.35) and FN (60.21 ± 7.94) systems compared to that of the F5 system (28.39 ± 8.44) (Fig. 3). Maximum plant growth requires optimal relative humidity in the range of 50 to 70 % (Tibbitts and Bottenberg 1976; Kang et al. 2016), and particularly lettuce up to 85 % (Chia and Lim 2022). The relative air humidity values were up to 75 % in the first month for all systems. It then decreased to the lower limit of 50%, and for the F5 system it was below the lower limit for the rest of the months (Fig. 3).

The optimum pH for good uptake of nutrients for most plant crops is 5.5 – 6.6 (Trejo-Téllez et al. 2012; Goddek et al. 2015), and for the development of the genetic potential of fish, between 7.0 and 9.0 (Boyd et al. 1979). Nitrifying bacteria require a high pH value (> 7), and the optimal pH range for the entire aquaponic system is between 6.0 and 8.0 (Medina 2014).

Figure 3: Mean values of relative air humidity for aquaponic systems F5, LC, and FN, for a period of four months in 2023. Asterisks indicate significant differences in mean values between the LC and F5 systems (* - $p < 0.05$ and * - $p < 0.001$). Red dashed lines indicate the upper and lower permissible limits of relative air humidity for maximum plant growth.**

The mean pH values for all three systems were closer to the upper limit. The pH values (8.91 ± 0.30) in the LC system were significantly higher ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$) compared to F5 and FN (8.47 ± 0.33 ; 8.34 ± 0.31 respectively) in January. The pH values for the F5 system (8.93 ± 0.34) were significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) in the 7th month of observation, compared to the average values of the LC (8.02 ± 0.16) and FN systems (8.20 ± 0.14) (Fig. 4, A).

In aquaponic systems, the pH of the water is affected by fish metabolism, food residues, and temperature changes (Defa et al. 2019). Increasing the water temperature and pH leads to an increase in the concentration of toxic NH_3 (Popma et al. 1999; Medina 2014).

Figure 4: Mean values of water pH (A) and DO (B) for systems F5, LC and FN, over a 7-month period in 2023. In panel A, asterisks indicate significant differences in mean pH values between the LC system and the other two systems (* - $p < 0.05$ and ** - $p < 0.01$); and ## ($p < 0.01$), those between F5 and the other LC and FN systems. In panel B, asterisks indicate significant differences in mean DO values (*) between F5 and the other two systems. Red dashed lines indicate the upper and lower permissible limits for pH and DO.**

DO is one of the most important environmental parameters that can be strictly regulated and controlled (Wedemeyer 2001). Its concentration in water for the needs of fish and plants should be in the range of 5 – 11 mg/L, however, the optimal amount is at least 6 mg/L (Timmons and Losordo 1994; Nelson 2008; Trejo-Téllez et al. 2012). In our studies, the DO values (mg/L) in the three systems were closer to the lower limit, with the values in the F5 system (5.76 ± 0.54) being lowest ($p < 0.001$) in the 7th month of the study in comparison with the other two LC and FN systems (7.45 ± 0.14 ; 7.64 ± 0.37 respectively) (Fig. 4, B).

Other important factors in the symbiosis between fish, beneficial bacteria and plants are the concentrations of ammonia, nitrite and nitrate. Ammonia is toxic to all types of fish and its concentration is directly proportional to the changes in pH and water temperature. In the observed systems, the concentration of ammonia initially increased, followed by an increase in the nitrite level, then an increase in the concentration of nitrate and a decrease in that of nitrite. During the second and third months of monitoring, the highest concentration of toxic non-ionized ammonia (NH_3) was 0.86 mg/L, that of nitrites 0.88 mg/L and ammonium-nitrogen ($\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$) 0.46 mg/L, whereas the nitrate levels in the seventh month ranged from 55.4 to over 66 mg/L in the LC system.

In order for an aquaponic system to function well, the ammonia NH_3 (ammonia nitrogen) concentration levels for tilapia need to be 0 – 0.8 mg/L; for aquaponics, below 0.01 mg/L; and NO_2^- (nitrites), 0 – 1 mg/L (Timmons et Losordo, 1994; Georgiev 2002; Rakocy et al. 2003; Nelson 2008; Supajaruwong et al. 2021), and NO_3^- (nitrates), up to 42.9 mg/L (Rakocy et al. 2003). The values measured in the F5 and FN systems were similar and did not exceed the permissible limits of these indicators.

Conclusion

1. The air temperature is optimal for maximum growth of fish and lettuce for all three aquaponic systems. Fish water temperature changed with air temperature and the changes were greatest for the LC and F5 systems for the 7th month of the study. The most variable is the air temperature for the F5 system.
2. The high pH values close to the upper allowable limit at the entire research period for the three aquaponic systems could be the cause of the increase in the concentration of toxic ammonia at the fish water temperature increases and for the disturbances in the normal growth of the plants.
3. Low values of DO concentration, close to the lower limit for fish and plant needs for all systems throughout the study period, may cause disturbances in fish and plant development.
4. The high levels of un-ionized ammonia concentration above the upper limit of the range (0 – 0.8 mg/L) for tilapia in the LC and FN systems were probably due to the high pH values.
5. The high concentration of nitrites above the upper limit of permissible values for nitrites (0 - 1.0 mg/L) for the LC system is probably due to the high concentrations of non-ionized ammonia.
6. The F5 system is the most labile, and the changes of the studied factors are the largest in it.

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